

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGROTOURISM AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Asgarov T.

ABSTRACT

Agrotourism, as a sector formed by the combination of tourism and agriculture, has great potential for both social and economic development. At the same time, it is an innovative type of tourism that creates conditions for rural communities to earn additional income and create jobs. This type of tourism is also of particular importance in terms of the use of natural resources in rural areas, the preservation of sustainable cultural heritage and traditions, and environmental protection. In addition, issues such as economic diversification in regions, social integration, and improving the social living standards of local communities through agrotourism also come to the fore.

Keywords: Agrotourism, economic growth, regions, development, environment.

Introduction. The tourism sector has played an important role in the social and economic development of Azerbaijan. The favorable location of Azerbaijan on the world map, its natural resources, the perfection of its nature and climate have created the basis for its being in the center of attention. The first journeys were related to trade, religion, politics, etc. Trade caravans passing through the country can be considered as the first journeys. The Great Silk Road, part of which passed through the territory of Azerbaijan, made a great contribution to the cultural, spiritual and material development of the country.

The importance of agritourism and its relationship with socio-economic development can be explained by the following main aspects:

1. Economic progress and source of income

Agrotourism provides a source of income for entrepreneurs engaged in agriculture in addition to their main activities. It is considered important mainly in mountainous and foothill regions, as the interest of tourists helps to sell local products and promote rural life experiences [1-8]. The sale of agricultural products, the organization of accommodation and stay of tourists in rural homes, the provision of local food and other rural activities provide an income stream. This promotes economic diversification, especially in rural areas, and strengthens the existing economic structure. Tourists who use this type of tourism are mainly those with a medium budget.

The agrotourism sector reduces unemployment in rural areas. New jobs are created as a result of agrotourism activities. As a result, local youth and residents in need of work continue to live in villages. According to the SME Agency, the opening of 15 rural guest houses in Ismayilli district in Azerbaijan in 2021 and the planning of about 50 new initiatives in other regions are the results of the work done in this direction. This increases the economic activity of the regions and slows down urbanization processes.

To reduce its dependence on oil, Azerbaijan prioritizes tourism, including agrotourism, in its "Azerbaijan 2030" National Goals. This sector activates the potential of regions, increases export revenues, and accelerates the economic recovery process after the pandemic. According to estimates, the value of the global agrotourism market is expected to reach \$60 billion by 2027[10].

2. Social development and cultural heritage protection

Agrotourism helps to promote and preserve local traditions and cultural heritage. Tourists experience rural life and learn about national culture, which keeps the cultural heritage of local communities alive. Agrotourism activities strengthen social ties and cooperation between rural communities. Bringing local people together through tourism supports social integration and increases the well-being of the community. Rural festivals, culinary presentations and crafts organized for tourists play a major role in promoting cultural heritage. This creates both social cohesion and economic value.

3. International experience and prospects

Globally many countries are using agritourism as a successful model. The agritourism sector has shown high results in terms of cultural heritage preservation, local community development, and economic growth. The development of agritourism in Azerbaijan is also considered a promising area for increasing the country's competitiveness in the global tourism market.

Steps have been taken to develop a "Strategic Roadmap" for the development of agritourism in Azerbaijan and a guidebook jointly with the US Agency for International Development (USAID). The application of foreign experiences (for example, the role of associations in Italy and Germany), improvement of legislation, and grant support to business entities are helping to structure this sector [9].

4. Ecological and Sustainable Development.

Properly planned Agrotourism projects create conditions for the sustainable use of natural resources and the protection and use of ecological balance. Tourism activities in rural areas support educational work towards the protection and restoration of nature.

Agrotourism plays an important role in renewing infrastructure in rural areas, creating new service areas, and stimulating overall regional development. The development of this sector paves the way for the economic diversification of regions and contributes to the development of the non-oil sector of the country's economy.

5. Development of rural infrastructure

The development of agrotourism also creates conditions for the implementation of major infrastructure

projects such as roads, water, and electricity. For example, in Italy and Germany, the construction of rural roads and the establishment of tourism centers with state support have radically changed the socio-economic life of villages. In Azerbaijan, "smart village" projects and programs of the State Tourism Agency envisage progress in this direction [9,10].

The agrotourism sector, which emerged from the synthesis of tourism and agriculture sectors in our country, has high potential due to the country's rich natural resources, climate diversity and cultural heritage. Support programs and legislative acts implemented by the state are important steps for the development of this sector. Thanks to pilot projects and initiatives in various regions, local communities have achieved positive results such as additional sources of income and the creation of new jobs.

As a result of the conducted research, it became clear that the interest in this sector among the citizens of our country is at a low level [7,8]. In our country, there are problems such as the lack of infrastructure development at any level, the shortage of specialists in this field, the weakness of marketing and promotional activities, as well as the failure to fully meet standard and quality requirements. At the same time, there are few facilities operating in this field. These circumstances hinder the wider application and development of agrotourism. This trend is observed in the Soviet countries, but Georgia and Belarus are exceptions. These countries have been paying great attention to agrotourism in recent years. In Belarus, people who want to engage in agrotourism are provided with a 7% annual loan, cheap land and necessary technical support by the state for 7 years.

Agrotourism is rapidly growing in many countries around the world, becoming an important part of the tourism industry. Its popularity is due to people's desire to relax outdoors, experience rural lifestyles, and support environmentally sustainable practices.

Western Europe is considered the main region for the development of agrotourism. In France, Italy, Spain, Germany and other countries, agrotourism began to develop actively in the second half of the 20th century. The economic crises in agriculture prompted farmers to look for additional sources of income, and agrotourism acted as an effective solution. State support and the creation of specialized associations led to the transformation of agrotourism into a profitable sector of the economy.

Agrotourism is also growing rapidly in the United States, providing opportunities for tourists to experience rural life and participate in agricultural activities. Farmers invite guests to participate in agricultural work, conduct farm tours, taste local products, and participate in other events. This supports local farms and popularizes the rural lifestyle. In some cases, tourists can work on farms in exchange for housing and meals. Thanks to this, they can integrate themselves more deeply into rural culture and life.

In Japan, agrotourism activities provide tourists with opportunities to experience rural life. Staying with farmers' families and participating in traditional agricultural events and festivals are popular. For example,

tourists can join in the harvest, learn traditional crafts, or attend local festivals. Urban agritourism is developing in Japan. Here, farms are located within cities. This allows tourists to easily access agricultural experiences without leaving the urban environment.

In China, agrotourism has become an important tool for preventing urban-rural fragmentation, improving the social well-being of rural people, and preserving cultural heritage. Different regions of the country offer unique agrotourism routes that promote the development of rural areas.

In Eastern European countries, especially in Poland, Hungary and the Czech Republic, agrotourism began to develop after the 2000s. Agrotourism is seen here as a tool for diversifying the rural economy, creating jobs and preserving cultural traditions.

Result. In countries where agrotourism is developed, in Italy, France, Spain and other countries, the infrastructure is organized at a high level. Tourists going to rural areas can use convenient roads to get to the village and region they want. In our country, serious steps have been taken in recent years to improve the road infrastructure. However, the road infrastructure is still not at a good level, especially for tourists who want to go to remote villages, this creates a big problem and obstacle. Mainly, in Guba, Sheki, Gusar, Lankaran and other regions with great potential in terms of agrotourism, the road infrastructure should be brought to a high level. The poor condition of the roads results in tourists having difficulty accessing rural areas by car or public transport. The quality of the roads facilitates access to agrotourism facilities and attracts tourists. Good road infrastructure allows the products produced by the same farmers to be easily delivered to the market. In addition, it contributes to the organization of new and other catering facilities in the region where restaurants are located, which are the focus of investors' attention. For the development of agrotourism, it is important to have government projects, private sector investments and support from international financial institutions to improve road infrastructure.

References

1. Lebedko E.Ya., Kislova E.N., Torikov V.E. RURAL TOURISM - A NEW CHANCE FOR THE REVIVAL AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE VILLAGE // International Journal of Experimental Education. - 2012. - No. 5. - P. 43-44;
2. Dunets, A.N., Isaev, V.V., Bitter, N.V., Donskova, L.I., Revyakin, V.S., Bovtun, V.S., Petrakova, T.G., Gerasimova, O.Yu., Panin, E.L., & Kositsyna, A.V. (2009). Rural tourism business in the Altai Territory.
3. Demishkevich, G. M., Karpova, I. M., & Zhivotova, Zh. V. (2008). Organization of rural tourism based on peasant (farmer) and personal subsidiary farming.
4. Lebedeva, I. V., & Kopylova, S. L. (2017). Rural tourism. Methodological recommendations for the development of rural tourism in the Kaluga region.

5. Sarafanova, A. G., Shabalina, N. V., & Sarafanov, A. A. (2020). Rural and agritourism: approaches to definition. Modern problems of service and tourism.

6. Savitsky, O. G. (2015) Development of rural tourism using the example of the Krasnodar region: state, problems, prospects / O. G. Savitsky

7. Huseynova, S. (2023). COINTEGRATION ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

PARAMETERS BETWEEN RUSSIA AND AZERBAIJAN. *Sciences of Europe*, (110), 26-31.

8. Guliyev, R. R., & Huseynova, S. M. (2016). Research on Azerbaijan's import and annual GDP co-relation based on econometric models in the frame of joining WTO. *Journal of Contemporary Applied Mathematics-ISSN: 2222-5498*, 6(1).

9. <https://vergiler.az/news/economy/16998.html>

10. <https://agro.gov.az/az/news/0206231>